

KMP-1 kernel elongation ratio is 1.8, compared with 1.7 for Sona and 2.0 for Basmati 370. It recorded a volume expansion ratio of 4.9, compared with

4.2 of IR20 and 4.1 of J-192. Alkali value and amylose content equal those of IR20 (Table 2).

KMP-1 is gaining popularity, especially in the traditionally fine-grain rice growing districts of Karnataka. ✎

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Disease resistance

Reaction of tall and dwarf rice varieties to bacterial leaf blight

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A collection of 104 rice varieties, 74 dwarf and 30 tall, were evaluated for reaction to bacterial leaf blight *Xanthomonas oryzae* (BLB) during 1981-82 kharif at the Pattambi RRS.

Varieties were dry seeded in dryland nursery beds, then irrigated and maintained under wet conditions. Fertilizer was applied at 120-60-40 kg NPK/ha. At panicle initiation, plants were clip inoculated with BLB suspension. Disease incidence was recorded 15 days after 50% flowering, using the Standard Evaluation System for Rice.

No entry was free of infection, 33 showed resistant to moderately resistant reactions, 58 moderately susceptible to susceptible, and 13 highly susceptible (see table). Of the tall varieties tested, 50% were susceptible or highly susceptible; 65% of these were local varieties. ✎

Reaction^a of rice varieties or cultures to bacterial leaf blight. 1981-82 kharif, Pattambi Rice Research Station, Kerala, India.

Resistance rating	Dwarf varieties	Tall varieties
R	IR8-68, IR5, Jayanthi, Bhadra, Jagannath, Sakthi	H4, Pokkali, Malinga, Mashoory, Bluebonnet, Mala, Bhavani
MR	IR8, IR20, IR22, IR26, IR42, Cul. 4, Cul. 23178, Cul. 23332-2, Cul. 23372, BR51, Hema, Pankaj, Annapoorna, Rasi, Jamuna, Suma, Pennai, Suphala	Kolappala, Vyttila I
MS	IR28, IR30, IR32, IR34, PR106, Cul. 1-5-4, Cul. 1999, Au-1, Jaya, Sona, Vijaya, Vani, Rohini, Jyothy, Karuma, Cauveri, Madhu, Hamsa, Supriya, Kumar, Parijath, Rajendra, Kalinga I	H105, Basmathi, Ptb 1, Ptb 2, Ptb 5, Vyttila-11
S	IR36, Cul. 3, Cul. 1180, Cul. 12035, Cul. 12814, Cul. 1065, Cul. 7944, MN54-42, Aswathy, Sabary, Satya, Soorya, Suhasini, Rajeswari, DGWG, Triveni, Bala, Krishna, Ratna, Anupama, Kannagi, Kalinga 11	Purple, Chennellu, Ptb 8, Ptb 9, Ptb 22, Ptb 28, Ptb 32
HS	IR1552, T(N) 1, Bharathy, Kanchi, Padma	Suvarna modan, Cul. 25064, Cul. 1907, Ptb 10, Ptb 26, Ptb 29, Ptb 30

^aR = resistant, MR = moderately resistant, MS = moderately susceptible, S = susceptible, HS = highly susceptible.

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Insect resistance

Sesamia inferens — a serious pest of rice in Uttar Pradesh Hills, India

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Stem borer epidemics in pockets of the Uttar Pradesh Hills occur regularly in irrigated valleys and in direct-seeded dryland rice. In a survey of the Kumaon hills and of experimental fields of

VLHA, 50-60% infestations were recorded.

The pest has been identified as *Sesamia inferens* Wlk (pink stem borer). In other parts of India, *Tryporyza incertulas* Wlk (yellow stem borer) has been reported a major problem. Pink stem borers also attack several other crops grown in this region: ragi (*Eleusine coracana*), Japanese barnyard millet (*Echinochloa frumentacea*), and maize (*Zea mays*).

Low infestation on rice occurs in early July, when larvae cause deadhearts in seedlings. Severe infestations occur in September, with maximum whiteheads in late September.

To identify sources of pink borer resistance, a large number of genotypes were screened. Some promising entries that showed low infestation were also screened under partially artificial conditions. IR8866-30-3, IR9202-56-1, and IR5908-21-2-1 showed high resistance.

In experiments on chemical control, sprays of chlorpyrifos 20 EC, monocrotophos, and carbaryl 50 WP were effective. ✎